

Stability Analysis of Some Modified Brusselators—Part II

P. N. JHA and R. K. PRASAD*

Department of Chemistry, L. S. College, Bihar University, Muzaffarpur-842 001

Manuscript received 9 June 1981, revised 2 March 1983, accepted 1 July 1983

The stability/instability of some modified Brusselator models have been examined theoretically. Two modifications have been considered, in one of which roles of X and Y are reversed while in the other the termolecular step is decomposed into two bimolecular steps involving a third intermediate Z. The stability zones as functions of concentration parameters of the inputs (A and B) as well as diffusion coefficients of the intermediates have been expressed graphically. The significance of these models with respect to chemical and biological points of view has been described.

In an earlier paper¹ we examined the stability/instability of a chemical kinetic model—the Brusselator²⁻⁵ in the phase plane. Tyson⁶ suggested that a modified Brusselator in which the roles of the intermediates X and Y are reversed in the last two steps could have an interesting interpretation in terms of the “standard mitogen model” used by biologists to understand the control of cell divisions⁷. For this reason this modification of original Brusselator as represented below has been subjected to a similar study in the present paper.

These kinetic models, even though of great theoretical significance, are open to criticism as being physically unrealistic because of a termolecular step (step 3) in the mechanism. Tyson⁶ has sidestepped the objectionable feature by introducing another intermediate Z in the original Brusselator,

Thus, the new model (II) which is another modification of the Brusselator, consisting of only bimolecular steps becomes

Stability behaviour of the models :

The model I : Setting all rate constants equal to unity, the rate equations for the variables X and Y under conditions of efficient stirring are represented as :

$$\dot{X} = A - BX - XY \quad \dots \text{ (1)}$$

$$\dot{Y} = BX + XY^2 - Y \quad \dots \text{ (2)}$$

where A, B, X and Y represent the concentrations of the respective chemical species. This leads to the following singular points (steady state of X and Y) in the phase plane :

$$\begin{array}{l} X_0 = \frac{A}{A^2 + B} \\ Y_0 = A \end{array} \quad \dots \text{ (3)}$$

Here the Jacobians are :

$$\left(\frac{\partial \dot{X}}{\partial X} \right)_0 = -B - Y_0^2 = -B - A^2,$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial \dot{X}}{\partial Y} \right)_0 = -2X_0 Y_0 = -\frac{2A^2}{A^2 + B},$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial \dot{Y}}{\partial X} \right)_0 = B + Y_0^2 = B + A^2,$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial \dot{Y}}{\partial Y} \right)_0 = 2X_0 Y_0 - 1 = \left(\frac{2A^2}{A^2 + B} \right) - 1.$$

Linear stability analysis of the steady state (considering small perturbations $x = X - X_0$, $y = Y - Y_0$) yields the following characteristic equation :

$$\lambda^2 - \text{Tr} \cdot \lambda + \Delta = 0 \quad \dots \text{ (4)}$$

where

$$\text{Tr} = \left(\frac{\partial \dot{X}}{\partial X} \right)_0 + \left(\frac{\partial \dot{Y}}{\partial Y} \right)_0 = -(A^2 + B) + \frac{2A^2}{A^2 + B} - 1,$$

$$\Delta = \left(\frac{\partial \dot{X}}{\partial X} \right)_0 \cdot \left(\frac{\partial \dot{Y}}{\partial Y} \right)_0 - \left(\frac{\partial \dot{X}}{\partial Y} \right)_0 \cdot \left(\frac{\partial \dot{Y}}{\partial X} \right)_0 = B + A^2$$

and λ is called the characteristic value.

Condition for instability : As discussed in the earlier paper, the steady state will be asymptotically stable if, and only if, both $\text{Tr} < 0$ and $\Delta > 0$. Instability will arise if $\text{Tr} > 0$ or $\Delta < 0$. Since A and B represent here concentration terms, Δ cannot be

* Author for correspondences.

$\langle 0$. Thus in the present case, the steady state will be unstable if and only if

$$B + A^2 - \frac{2A^2}{A^2 + B} + 1 < 0$$

i.e., $A^2 - B > (B + A^2)^2$

This condition is quite satisfactory only for $0 < A < 1$ and $0 < B < 0.125$. The zone of instability can be represented by a small rectangle.

Diffusion included: Now let us consider a case in which the reaction vessel is not stirred. Under this circumstances, the intermediates X and Y are transported by diffusion leading to inhomogeneity of the system. Thus the equations of motion assume the form :

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{X} &= F(X, Y) + D_x \nabla^2 X \\ \dot{Y} &= G(X, Y) + D_y \nabla^2 Y \end{aligned} \quad \dots (5)$$

where $X = X(r, t)$, $Y = Y(r, t)$, $\nabla^2 =$ the Laplacian operator which in one dimension is $\partial^2 / \partial r^2$, $F(X, Y)$ and $G(X, Y)$ are the right-hand sides of equations (1) and (2), respectively, D_x and D_y are the respective diffusion coefficients of X and Y and they are all ≥ 0 and the cross diffusion coefficients D_{xy} and D_{yx} are negligibly small.

The homogeneous steady state (HSS) of eq. (5) is given by $X_0 = \frac{A}{A^2 + B}$, $Y_0 = A$. Now let us first introduce the characteristic function of the Laplacian operator

$$\nabla^2 f_k(r) = -k^2 f_k(r) \quad \dots (6)$$

where k is the characteristic eigen value corresponding to the eigen function $f_k(r)$. The spectrum of the characteristic values k depend on the geometry and boundary conditions applied to (6). Usually k is real⁶, so that $k^2 \geq 0$.

The variational equation obtained on the basis of the same treatment is

$$\lambda^2 + d_1 \lambda + d_2 = 0 \quad \dots (7)$$

where

$$d_1 = k^2 I_1 - I_2, \quad d_2 = k^4 I_3 - k^2 I_4 + I_5$$

and

$$I_1 = D_x + D_y, \quad I_2 = \left(\frac{\partial F}{\partial X}\right)_0 + \left(\frac{\partial G}{\partial Y}\right)_0 = -(A^2 + B) + \frac{2A^2}{A^2 + B} - 1,$$

$$I_3 = D_x D_y,$$

$$I_4 = \left(\frac{\partial F}{\partial X}\right)_0 \cdot D_y - \left(\frac{\partial G}{\partial Y}\right)_0 \cdot D_x = -(A^2 + B) D_y + \left(\frac{2A^2}{A^2 + B} - 1\right) D_x$$

$$I_5 = \left(\frac{\partial F}{\partial X}\right)_0 \cdot \left(\frac{\partial G}{\partial Y}\right)_0 - \left(\frac{\partial F}{\partial Y}\right)_0 \cdot \left(\frac{\partial G}{\partial X}\right)_0 = B + A^2$$

As before the HSS will be asymptotically stable if, and only if both $d_1 > 0$ and $d_2 > 0$. Since $k^2 \geq 0$, we need consider only the signs of $I_1, \dots, I_5$. Firstly $I_1, I_5 \geq 0$, since the diffusion coefficients are always ≥ 0 . For modes, foci and centres, I_5 must

be > 0 . It can be < 0 for saddle points. Although saddle points are always essentially unstable, they are not of interest to us in the present work. We may have I_2 and $I_4 > 0$ or < 0 so that there are two chances for instability : $d_1 < 0$ and/or $d_2 < 0$. Thus, if the model (I) is coupled with diffusion, the HSS $X(r, t) = X_0 = A / (A^2 + B)$, $Y(r, t) = Y_0 = A$ can become unstable if

$$(i) \quad A^2 - B > (B + A^2)^2 + (A^2 + B)(k^2 D_x + k^2 D_y)$$

or if

$$(ii) \quad \frac{2A^2}{A^2 + B} > (A^2 + B)k^2 D_y (k^2 D_x)^{-1} + k^2 D_y + 1$$

Detailed calculations show that these conditions are satisfied for $0 < A < 1$ and $0 < B < 0.115$ corresponding to $k^2 = 0.05$, $D_x = D_y = 0.1$.

The model II: The three non-linear differential equations representing the motion are

$$\dot{X} = A - BX + 2X^2 + 2Z + 2Y - X \quad \dots (8a)$$

$$\dot{Y} = BX - ZY \quad \dots (8b)$$

$$\dot{Z} = X^2 - Z \quad \dots (8c)$$

where A, B, X, Y and Z have their usual significance. This leads to the following singular points :

$$X_0 = A, \quad Y_0 = B/A, \quad Z_0 = A^2 \quad \dots (9)$$

Here the Jacobians are :

$$\left(\frac{\partial \dot{X}}{\partial X}\right)_0 = -B - 4X_0 - 1 = -B - 4A - 1,$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial \dot{X}}{\partial Y}\right)_0 = Z_0 = A^2,$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial \dot{X}}{\partial Z}\right)_0 = 2 + Y_0 = 2 + B/A,$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial \dot{Y}}{\partial X}\right)_0 = B,$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial \dot{Y}}{\partial Y}\right)_0 = -Z_0 = -A^2,$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial \dot{Y}}{\partial Z}\right)_0 = -Y_0 = -B/A,$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial \dot{Z}}{\partial X}\right)_0 = 2X_0 = 2A,$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial \dot{Z}}{\partial Y}\right)_0 = 0,$$

$$\left(\frac{\partial \dot{Z}}{\partial Z}\right)_0 = -1,$$

Linear stability analysis leads to the following characteristic equation :

$$\lambda^3 + (A^2 + 4A + B + 2)\lambda^2 + (4A^3 + 2A^2 - B + 1)\lambda + A^2 = 0 \quad \dots (10)$$

Condition for instability: The necessary and sufficient condition for instability, according to Routh-Hurwitz criteria⁹ is that any one of the

coefficients for the various powers of λ be negative. In the present case, this means

$$B > 4A^3 + 2A^2 + 1.$$

This, for $A=1$, reduces to the condition $B > 7$.

The zones of instability can be shown graphically in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1

The following points are to be noted from Fig. 1.

- (i) For every value of A , there is a critical value of B (i.e., B_c) and for $B > B_c$, the system will be unstable.
- (ii) For the homogeneous steady state, the modified Brusselator (II) tends to be stable at larger values of A for a larger variation of B . At smaller values of A , the point of marginal stability is quickly reached.

Including diffusion: The equations of motion for this model take the form :

$$\dot{X} = F(X, Y, Z) + D_x \nabla^2 X \quad \dots (11a)$$

$$\dot{Y} = G(X, Y, Z) + D_y \nabla^2 Y \quad \dots (11b)$$

$$\dot{Z} = H(X, Y, Z) + D_z \nabla^2 Z \quad \dots (11c)$$

A linear stability analysis similar to that described above leads to the following characteristic equation :

$$\lambda^3 + \lambda^2 \{A^3 + 4A + B + 2 + k^2(D_x + D_y + D_z)\} + \lambda \{4A^3 + 2A^2 + 1 - B(1 - k^2 D_y - k^2 D_x) + k^2 D_y(4A + 2) + k^2 D_x(4A + 1) + k^2 D_x(A^3 + 1) + k^4 D_x D_y + k^4 D_x D_z + k^4 D_y D_x\} + \{-Bk^2 D_y(1 - k^2 D_x) + k^2 D_x A^3(1 + 4A) + k^2 D_y + k^4 D_y D_x(4A + 1) + k^4 D_x D_x(A^3 + k^2 D_y) + k^4 D_x(k^2 D_y + A^3)\} = 0 \quad \dots (12)$$

According to Routh-Hurwitz criteria, which is applicable to higher order polynomials, there will be

two conditions when the system will become unstable with respect to inhomogeneous perturbations :

$$(i). B > \frac{4A^3 + 2A^2 + 1 + k^2 D_y(4A + 2) + k^2 D_x(4A + 1) + k^2 D_x(A^3 + 1) + k^4 D_x D_y + k^4 D_x D_z + k^4 D_y D_x}{1 - k^2(D_y + D_x)}$$

$$and \quad (ii). B > \frac{k^2 D_x A^3(1 + 4A) + k^2 D_y + k^4 D_y D_x(4A + 1) + k^4 D_x D_x(A^3 + k^2 D_y) + k^2 D_x(k^2 D_y + A^3)}{k^2 D_y(1 - k^2 D_x)}$$

The first criteria reduces to the familiar $B > 4A^3 + 2A^2 + 1$ for homogeneous ($k=0$) perturbations. We can see from (ii) that the HSS can become unstable with respect to spatially inhomogeneous perturbations for $A=1, D_x=1, D_y=0.1, D_z=0.1$.

This fact is illustrated in Fig. 2 where the zones of stability/instability are indicated by plotting B against the various positive and negative values of k .

Fig. 2

The curves are perfectly symmetrical about the B -axis. This modification, however, differs from the original Brusselator in that the two curves due to two different criteria (i) and (ii) do not intersect indicating no common zone of instability of the system.

Discussion

The analysis given above indicates the conditions when the steady state (X_0, Y_0) may become unstable with respect to small perturbations. These conditions are governed by the values of certain parameters such as reactant concentrations (A and B) besides the boundary conditions (eigen values k), in case of a non-homogeneous medium.

The model I, as has been mentioned earlier, acquires significance in biology in that it finds interesting interpretation for the standard 'mitogen model' for the control of cell divisions. Let X represent the mitogen which, when exceeding a certain critical concentration, triggers the cellular process resulting in cell division. It is produced at a constant rate from A within the cytoplasm. It is

then incorporated into the nucleus in an inactive form Y at a rate proportional to its own concentration. Further, Y catalyses its own production so that during mitosis Y increases abruptly at the expense of X. This process brings the concentration of X down well below the critical value. Finally Y breaks down spontaneously and the cycle repeats itself.

From the chemical point of view also this model may be considered to be significant in as much as it may correspond to the mechanism of enzyme catalysed glycolysis. Mechanism for this reaction as proposed by Sel'kov¹⁰ is as follows :

where ATP=adenosine triphosphate, ADP=adenosine diphosphate, E_1^* =inactive form of the enzyme (phosphofructokinase), E_1^* =active form of the enzyme, ATPE^* =enzymatic complex, γ =number of ADP molecules necessary to activate the enzyme.

If X and Y in the model are supposed to stand for ATP and ADP, respectively and if $\gamma=2$, then steps (ii), (iii) and (iv) combined together may correspond to the termolecular autocatalytic step (3) of the model. Sel'kov using the kinetic equations corresponding to this mechanism developed the criteria of instability with respect to both homogeneous and inhomogeneous perturbations. Under the conditions of temporal oscillation in the homogeneous phase, the frequency ω was derived and was found to be given by :

$$\omega = k_2 \sqrt{\gamma - 1} \quad \dots \text{ (13)}$$

Sel'kov determined the value of $k_2 = 4 \times 10^{-2} \text{ sec}^{-1}$. Using this value of k_2 and putting $\gamma=2$ in equation (13) it is very interesting to note that the frequency of oscillations in glycolysis is found to be equal to 2.4 min^{-1} so that the period of oscillations is 2.6 minutes ($T=2\pi/\omega$). This value is in agreement with the experimental value of 3.5 minutes found by Hess¹¹.

As has been said earlier, the original Brusselator has been criticised only on the ground that it contains a termolecular step $2X + Y \rightarrow 3X$. The model (II) meets the criticism fairly well wherein the termolecular step is regarded, to a good approximation, as the overall step of several realistic bimolecular and unimolecular steps. The steps $2X \rightarrow Z$ followed by $Z + Y \rightarrow 3X$ may, for example, very well represent dimerisation ($Z=X_2$) followed by chemical interaction with Y. This can also represent an enzymatic chain reaction of the type :

It has been shown by Goldbeter, Boiteux and Hess¹² that for some values of some reaction parameters, the glycolytic oscillator will present a third order molecularity if more than two sub units are considered for the enzyme.

Investigations of the conditions that may lead to limit cycle behaviour of these models will form the part of further work which is in progress.

Acknowledgement

One of the authors (P.N.J.) is grateful to U.G.C., New Delhi for a Junior Research Fellowship.

References

1. P. N. JHA and R. K. PRASAD, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1981, **58**, 377.
2. R. LEFVEVER, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1968, **49**, 4977.
3. I. PRIGOGINE and R. LEFVEVER, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1968, **48**, 1695.
4. R. LEFVEVER and G. NICOLIS, *J. Theor. Biol.*, 1971, **30**, 267.
5. J. J. TYSON, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1978, **58**, 3919.
6. J. J. TYSON and J. C. LIGHT, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1973, **59**, 4164.
7. J. M. MITCHISON, "The Biology of Cell Cycle", Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 1971.
8. J. I. GMITRO and L. E. SCRIVER, in "Intracellular Transport", (Ed.) K. B. WARREN, Academic Press, New York, 1966.
9. F. R. GRANMACHER, "Theory of Matrices", Chelsea, New York, 1960.
10. E. E. SEL'KOV, *Eur. J. Biochem.*, 1968, **4**, 79.
11. B. HELL and A. BOITEUX, "Regulatory Functions of Biological Membranes", Elsevier, 1968, 148.
12. A. BOITEUX, B. HESS and A. GOLDBETER, "Faraday Symposia on Physical Chemistry of Oscillatory Phenomena", The Chemical Society, London, 1974.